

Sharing Knowledge with the Community on the Utilization of IT-Based Pyrolysis Technology for Independent Waste Management

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Keywords: Waste, Pyrolysis, Fuel, Control System	Abstrak
Submitted: 02/12/2024	The waste problem continues to increase along with population growth and consumption. Effective waste management is crucial to maintain environmental cleanliness and public health. This community service article aims to transfer knowledge to the community about the use of IT-based pyrolysis technology for independent waste management. The community will be introduced to the concept of pyrolysis, which is the process of decomposing organic waste into valuable products, such as bio-oil, bio-char, and gas. In addition, the community is expected to be trained to operate and maintain an IT-based pyrolysis system, which allows efficient monitoring and control of the process. Through this article, the public can understand and adopt IT-based pyrolysis technology to manage household waste independently. This will reduce the volume of waste disposed of in landfills, as well as produce products that can be reused. Thus, the community can contribute to the creation of a clean, healthy, and sustainable environment.
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INTRODUCTION

The waste problem is one of the biggest challenges faced by modern society. Along with population growth and increased consumption, the volume of waste produced continues to increase significantly (Parthasarathy et al., 2023). Ineffective waste management can cause various serious problems, such as environmental pollution, the spread of diseases, and damage to ecosystems (Kumaran & Sharma, 2020).

In Indonesia, the waste problem has become increasingly complex due to the lack of infrastructure and low public awareness regarding good waste management, although at some points there is already waste management, but in most areas there is still waste that has not been managed properly (Sari et al., 2023). Most of the garbage is still disposed of in the final landfill (TPA) Those that have exceeded their capacity, some are thrown into the river, from the upstream to the mouth of the river which finally goes to the sea.

This causes TPA become a source of environmental pollution and cause health problems for the surrounding community (Mitan et al., 2022).

In addition to the waste problem, the need for energy is also increasing, the dependence on fossil fuels as a major energy source has led to various environmental problems, such as climate change and air pollution. Therefore, it is necessary to find alternative solutions that are more sustainable and environmentally friendly to meet the energy needs of the community (Williams, 2021).

In this context, pyrolysis technology has emerged as one of the potential solutions to address waste and energy problems. Pyrolysis is the process of breaking down organic matter into valuable products, such as bio-oil, bio-char, and gas, through heating in an oxygen-free environment. This technology can be used to process various types of organic waste, including household waste, agricultural waste and industrial waste (Li et al., 2020).

Information technology integration (IT) in a pyrolysis system can improve the efficiency and effectiveness of the process. IT systems can be used to monitor and control temperature, pressure, and other parameters in real-time, resulting in quality pyrolysis products and reducing harmful gas emissions and minimizing technical risks if in direct contact with processing equipment (Lee et al., 2020).

Based on this background, the formulation of the problem in this community service article is how to transfer knowledge to the community about the use of IT-based pyrolysis technology for independent waste management. How to train the community to operate and maintain an IT-based pyrolysis system independently. How to increase public awareness about the importance of effective waste management and the use of renewable energy (Afriliana et al., 2025).

To answer the formulation of this problem, this article offers a solution in the form of literacy related to community service activities that aims to transfer knowledge related to waste management with IT-based pyrolysis technology (Chhabra et al., 2016). The community will be introduced to the concept of pyrolysis, which is the process of decomposing organic waste into valuable products. They will be invited to understand the benefits of pyrolysis in reducing waste volume and producing renewable energy. Training and mentoring, the community will be trained to operate and maintain an IT-based pyrolysis system. They will be provided with practical knowledge and skills in using this technology to manage household waste independently. Increased awareness, through this activity, it is hoped that the community can increase awareness about the importance of effective waste management and the use of renewable energy. They will be invited to actively participate in creating a clean, healthy, and sustainable environment (R & M, 2013).

By reading this article, the public can follow and understand the trend of adopting IT-based pyrolysis technology to manage household waste independently. This will reduce the volume of waste disposed of into the TPA, produce products that can be reused, and increase public awareness of the importance of waste management, which has a positive effect on the environment and sustainable energy.

COMMUNITY SERVICE METHODS

Seminars and workshops, holding seminars and workshops that discuss waste problems, the potential of IT-based pyrolysis technology, and its benefits for society and the environment.

Social media, using social media to disseminate information about IT-based pyrolysis technology, and inviting the public to participate in community service activities.

The exhibition held an exhibition that displayed IT-based pyrolysis technology and products produced from the pyrolysis process.

Providing learning materials that are easy to understand and accessible to the public regarding IT-based pyrolysis technology. Compile a printed learning module that contains complete information about IT-based pyrolysis technology, from basic theory to practical guidance on system operation and maintenance. Develop digital learning modules that can be accessed via computers or mobile devices. Digital modules can contain video tutorials, animations, or interactive simulations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We want to realize this community service activity with a target of at least 50 participants consisting of 25 men and women of productive age. The concept of this activity is, at least participants must first understand what the concept of Pyrolysis is, so that participants are able to understand the potential of the technology, including the results of recycling as shown in figure 1.

(Source: kencanaonline.com)

Figure 1. The Concept of Pyrolysis

IT-based pyrolysis system operation skills. In addition to understanding the concept, participants also understand various functions of pyrolysis equipment components in order to successfully master basic skills in operating and maintaining an IT-based pyrolysis system. Through demonstrations and hands-on practice, participants are expected to be able to identify system components, set process parameters, and monitor and control through IT devices. They also understand the importance of maintaining the cleanliness and safety of the system to ensure the smooth process of pyrolysis.

(Source: <https://bestoncompany.com/id/small-pyrolysis-plant>)

Figure 2. The Concept of Pyrolysis

In addition, we will explain some pyrolysis devices based on their functions, such as reactors, heaters, condensers, containers and control systems as shown in table 1 below.

Table 1. Name and function of simple pyrolysis device

Tool Name	Function
Reactor	A container used to hold the raw materials to be heated. These reactors are made of strong and heat-resistant materials such as steel, <i>stainless steel</i> , or ceramics. The shape of the reactor varies greatly, depending on the type of process that will be carried out in it
Heating Devices	In the pyrolysis process, a heating device is needed to raise the temperature of the reactor until the target temperature is reached. Commonly used heating devices include gas stoves, electric stoves, or heating elements
Kondensor	In a pyrolysis system, the condenser plays an important role in converting the steam from heating the reactor back into a liquid. This process occurs because the condenser cools the vapor, so that the vapor condenses and transforms into a liquid
Containers	Containers or tanks are used to collect liquid products produced from the pyrolysis process. These tanks must be made of strong materials and resistant to chemicals contained in pyrolysis liquid products
Control System	The pyrolysis device uses a control system to regulate the temperature, pressure, and gas flow in the reactor. There are generally two types of these control systems: manual and automatic. Manual Control System <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The operator must manually regulate the temperature, pressure, and gas flow. 2. Requires high operator attention and expertise. 3. Suitable for small scale or research. Automatic Control System <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The system can automatically adjust the temperature, pressure, and gas flow based on pre-programmed settings. 2. More efficient and accurate. 3. Suitable for large scale or industry.

Table 2. Main Differences Between Automatic and Manual Control

Feature	Manual	Automatic
Tingkat Kontrol	Lower	Higher
Control Level	Lower	Higher
Efficiency	Lower	Higher
Accuracy	Lower	Higher
Scale	Small or research	Large or industrial

One of the encouraging achievements is the ability of participants to produce household-scale pyrolysis products independently. By using organic waste from the surrounding environment, participants succeeded in producing quality bio-oil and bio-char. These products are then used for various purposes, such as alternative fuels, organic fertilizers, or planting media. This success shows that IT-based pyrolysis technology can be accessed and implemented by the community independently.

Impact on the environment and society, this community service activity, if held, certainly has a significant positive impact on the environment and society. In terms of the environment, this activity contributes to reducing the volume of waste disposed of into the TPA. Organic waste, which was previously considered waste, can now be processed into valuable products through pyrolysis technology. This helps reduce the load TPA and prevent environmental pollution.

In addition, this activity also provides economic benefits for the community. The pyrolysis products produced can be used to meet daily needs or sold to supplement

income. People also become more independent in managing their own waste, thus reducing dependence on others.

Increasing public awareness, in addition to the direct impact, this activity also succeeded in increasing public awareness about the importance of effective waste management and the use of renewable energy. Participants became more concerned about the waste problem and were motivated to contribute to creating a clean and healthy environment. They also become agents of change in the surrounding environment, inviting family, friends, and neighbors to participate in independent waste management.

Challenges and evaluations, there are several challenges faced in the implementation of this activity. One of them is the limitation of resources, such as equipment and how to get raw materials to make a simple pyrolysis device. In addition, there are still several participants who need further assistance in operating an IT-based pyrolysis system.

To overcome these challenges, there needs to be support from various parties, such as local governments, universities, industry, entrepreneurs and the private sector. Support can be in the form of financial assistance, provision of equipment, or further training. In addition, it is also necessary to conduct periodic evaluations of the implementation of activities to identify potential improvements if constrained such as spare parts from the tool if it is possible to have errors or damage.

CONCLUSION

Conclusion

The writing of this community service article has succeeded in transferring knowledge and skills to the community regarding the use of IT-based pyrolysis technology for independent waste management. Participants were able to understand the concept of pyrolysis, operate an IT-based pyrolysis system, and produce valuable pyrolysis products. In 2025, there will be a lot of tutorials on the internet or social media applications and even use a little AI assistance in operating pyrolysis tools or making simple pyrolysis tools for households or MSMEs, making it easier for people to get references related to the manufacture of pyrolysis tools, both concepts, tools and materials to be used. This activity has a positive impact on the environment and society, as well as increasing public awareness about the importance of sustainable waste and energy management.

Suggestion

Based on the results and discussions above, some of the recommendations that can be submitted are the need for continuous support from various parties to ensure the sustainability of this community service program. It is necessary to carry out further training and more intensive assistance for participants in need. Further research and development related to IT-based pyrolysis technology is needed to improve its efficiency and effectiveness.

Pyrolysis that is well developed and researched can produce products such as fuel, waste from processed products can also be used as decorations that produce economic value, and in further research it is hoped that pyrolysis can be the best option for waste processing without waste.

It is necessary to carry out wider socialization and in-depth research support on IT-based pyrolysis technology to the public so that more and more people understand and adopt it. With a little knowledge and recommendations in this article, it is hoped that IT-based pyrolysis technology can be an effective and sustainable solution to overcome waste and energy problems in Indonesia.

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